

Kandinsky and Mishra's Synesthetic Approach in Portraying Music: A Comparative Analysis

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Abstract

The theoretical framework of this research delves into the complex and multifaceted relationship between music and painting, particularly in the context of synesthetic experiences. The confluence of music and painting has given rise to thought-provoking theories and discussions about the interconnectedness of these two artistic realms. This article aims to provide a conceptual framework for understanding paintings of music. The article addresses the commonalities and differences in the creative techniques and visual interpretations of Wassily Kandinsky and Sushil Mishra's portrayal of Western and Indian Classical music. Through the comparative analysis of Kandinsky and Mishra's approaches to depicting music in their art, it becomes evident that the intersection between music and painting can lead to a diverse spectrum of emotional and sensory experiences, engaging the readers in a profound connection to the art forms. The study suggests that these experiences are both for the creators and the audience, making the research more relatable.

Keywords: *Synaesthesia, Hindustani Raga Music, Painting, Abstract expressionism, Ragamala Paintings*

Introduction

The history of synaesthesia research is almost 200 years old. In 1812, Georg Tobias Ludwig was the first to work on it. 'Synaesthesia' is derived from the Greek word 'Syn - Aesthesis', which means 'together' and 'Sensation' or 'Perception'. Synaesthesia can be defined as a neurological condition where stimulation of one sensory pathway triggers another sensory pathway (Simner 2012). This kind of cross-connection in the brain causes different sensory experiences automatically and consistently. These experiences may be unique to each individual.

Many synaesthesia theories are presented as genetic theories, cross-models, matching theories, modularity theories, etc. Researchers found different combinations of synaesthesia, such as 'Coloured hearing', where sound gives rise to visual perception and smell gives rise to tactile sensation, and 'Chromesthesia- the Sound to Colour synaesthesia' associated with specific sounds with colours. (Cytowic, 2018; Calkins, 1893)

All the theories of synaesthesia are based on some core facts, such as some humans reported extraordinary sensations of colours, taste, shapes, etc., triggered by activities like reading, eating, listening, music, etc. For example, synaesthetes might see colours while listening to music. (Ward, Huckstep & Tsakanikos, 2006). Synaesthesia can result from the use of psychoactive drugs or is caused by a neurological dysfunction (Critchley 1994; Cytowic 1989). There is evidence of connections between auditory and miserable areas in the brain that exist in humans, known as the 'Sensory leakage theory' (Jacobs et al. 1981). Hence, synaesthesia is a condition of merging the senses or a cross-sensory experience with perceptual stimuli triggers. Different variants of synaesthesia can be seen in different humans.

Research Objective

The primary objective of this research is to compare and analyse the portrayal of Western music by Russian artist Wassily Kandinsky (1866- 1944) and Indian Raga music by Indian artist Sushil Mishra (1981 – 2021) in their respective paintings. The aim is to gain interpretations of music through visual imagery and understand how these artists translate the intangible aspects of music into concrete visual representations.

This research paper studies the interconnectedness of music and painting, exploring the perceptual and emotional associations that arise while experiencing both art forms concurrently. Drawing inspiration from historical and contemporary examples and synesthetic artistry, it seeks to contribute to the ongoing discourse on how music and painting intertwine, evoke emotions, inspire creativity, and enrich our understanding of the world.

This study involves a comparative analysis of Wassily Kandinsky's and Sushil Mishra's paintings, focusing on their portrayal of Western and Indian Raga music, respectively. The analysis examines the artistic techniques, application of Colour, composition, and symbolism the artists employ to convey the essence of music in their paintings. A qualitative approach is used to conduct this research, utilising visual analysis and comparative study methods.

Research Gap

While the existing literature has extensively discussed the synesthetic associations and artistic translations of music into paintings, a notable research gap remains. This gap lies in exploring the disparities in subjective experience of the artists and their emotional response between paintings and listening to music. Furthermore, there is a lack of research on the portrayal of Indian Classical Music in paintings apart from the Ragamala paintings. This research addresses these gaps by focusing on the abstract expression of the emotional responses elicited while listening to music and painting.

We will discuss some of the paintings by both artists in detail to understand the concept of the transformation of emotions and expressions as they moved between the realms of music and painting.

Methodology

This study is a comparative analysis with a qualitative approach to the synaesthetic paintings by Kandinsky and Sushil Mishra. The research is focused on four paintings from each artist from existing research publications; also, it can be an extension of Pyasi and Mishra's research work (2012) based on a

synaesthetic approach. As neither artist is alive, the researchers must depend on available sources. The researchers studied and analysed the paintings on the basis of fundamental principles of art.

Overview of Wassily Kandinsky's Work and the Musical influence

Fascinated with the emotional power of music, Kandinsky played the cello and the piano as a talented musician, seeking the analogies between Colour and sound. In 1911, a concert by Viennese composer Arnold Schoenberg turned the vision and working style of Russian artist Wassily Kandinsky, and he attempted to put order to tonal colours (Spinato).

1. Impression III (1911)ⁱ

The self-explanatory title Impression III (Concert) is considered one of the earliest (1911) and most striking examples of modern art's endeavour to fuse Colour and sound in a synesthetic experience and interpretation. It's evidence of the artist's great understanding of synaesthesia and Caliber to convert his new static perception into a marvellous artwork. Colours and forms successfully create energy and a sense of movement that depicts the Sonic qualities of Music. Vibrant hues convey the passion of the performance, while dynamic shapes and bold contrast give rise to rhythm and tone/ modulation of instruments

A dynamic wave of yellow paint flows across the painting like a great swell of sound that seemingly reverberates to and from. The upper half of the painting is an energetic black in a diagonal position. One can clearly understand this scene with an open black grand piano and the curved backs of the seated listeners and those standing along the wall.

Kandinsky creates the music experience without visual cues by giving up traditional re-presentation. Abstract forms create a more personalised and unique interpretation where viewers can engage their imagination. This involves the audience in the artistic process.

2. Improvisation 19 (1911)ⁱⁱ

A brilliant example of using Colour tones as melody and Shapes as instruments, this painting is dominated by a deep, mesmerising blue, suggesting the foundational bass line or the rich tone of a cello. The unique synaesthetic perspective of Kandinsky shows the Cross connection between the senses of sight and sound, which is evident in the rhythmic musical quality of this painting; the artist's interplay of shapes and hues invokes a sense of auditory experience and invites the audience to involve with his artwork on a multi-sensory level. In this painting, Deep blue

suggests a foundational bass line or the rich tone of a cello, where colour tones are used as Melody and shapes are used as instruments. Over the blue canvas, vibrant hues -greens, yellows, oranges, and reds are like instrumental lines, weaving in and out of the sonic tapestry.

The forms in Improvisation 19 resonate with the fluidness and dynamism of music. Circular and crescent shapes remain chimes and elongated. Strokes look like bows across the string.

This composition shows a deep connection with Music. To create a sense of balance, the artist used interplay of positive and negative space; it looks like dialogue between instruments. Variety of textured strokes, adding rhythmic variation and Mimicking the tempo and dynamics of a musical performance. Improvisation 19 does not present the actual image of a musical scene but expresses the essence of the listening experience. Viewers can enter Kandinsky's synesthetic world where shapes become instruments, Colors turn into notes, and the canvas looks like a stage for an unfolding symphony.

3. Composition VII (1913)ⁱⁱⁱ

Kandinsky's relationship with music is clearly visible in his works. This painting is also an orchestrated illustration of musical expressions which resemble a symphony, according to him. He also described it as his most complex piece.

This work looks like a cacophony of shapes and colours, portraying the complex musical framework of a symphony. The use of warm and cool colours evokes the tension and release of musical phrases, while the interplay of light and shadow suggests the ebb and flow of sonic intensity. The overall sense of dynamism and movement resonates with the energy of the orchestral performance, inviting the viewer to participate in the visual composition as if listening to a sonic journey.

4. Yellow- Red- Blue (1925)^{iv}

Yellow red blue is a very popular painting created by Kandinsky in 1925. It is said to be impacted with Arnold, Schoenberg's musical compositions. Like the other three paintings, the visual representation of musical tones and rhythms can be seen prominently through lines, shapes and colours. This painting depicts a balance of colours, forms and lines, the same as in musical composition. The artist used primary colours to create visual harmony and successfully represented different musical notes or chords. The German trickle shapes and lines represent the rhythm and movement in a piece of music and guide the viewer's eyes across the canvas, just like music guides a listener's emotions. Yellow is associated with the sound of a sharp and attention-grabbing trumpet. In this composition, a large yellow area represents a dominant bright note. Warm and dynamic red can be linked to the sound of a violin as the central red forms, adding energy and warmth like a melodious line. The blue areas provide a sense of depth and contrast, just like a bass line in music.

Sushil Mishra's Portrayal of Indian Raga Music in Art

Mishra, an amateur musician, believed that the abstraction in music should be conveyed through the abstract form of painting (Mishra, 2013). He studied Ragamala paintings, a series of illustrative artworks from medieval India. These diverse paintings portray various Indian musical RAGAS in different styles, with artists using raag and Ragini as central themes. They serve as a quintessential example of the fusion of art, poetry, and classical music in medieval India. However, the paintings prominently embody personification and explore the connection between emotion and the seasons in relation to Ragas and Raginis, rather than directly interpreting the sound and emotion of the music being performed.

In the literature review, the researchers found that Mishra was probably the first artist to paint Ragas of ICM in abstract expressionism. He shares the experience of articulating Ragas through colours and brush in the following words- "Painting awesome performances of Indian Classical Musicians is so tempting and pleasurable to be explained in words. The tonal variations of sound (swaras) are depicted by tones of various colours. I tried to correlate seven swaras with seven basic colours. Intricacies and simplicity of rhythmic patterns are displayed through bold and soft lines, strokes of brushes, and a spatula/palette knife. The subtleties and nuances of patterns of

notes and tonal variations used in any raga are sufficient enough to evoke inner expressions and emotions." (Pyasi and Mishra, 2019)

There is a difference between Indian and Western music theories. Unlike Western music, Indian music is partially pre-composed and more improvised. The spontaneity and improvisation of Indian music are the exclusive features that make the work portraying music even more spontaneous.

1. Raag Des (Pt. Nikhil Banerjee - Sitar)^v

Mishra applied vibrant colours with a palette knife to elucidate Des's romantic mood. The prominent use of warm hues, red, orange and yellow, symbolises the warmth and brightness often associated with the raga Des. These colours evoke emotions of energy, passion, and vibrancy, which are characteristics of this raga, typically played during the late afternoon or early evening, embodying a sense of serene joy.

The cool hues, blue and green, represent the calming and soothing aspects of the raga. These colours often suggest tranquillity and depth, indicating the raga's capacity to evoke a peaceful yet evocative atmosphere.

The fluid and dynamic brushstrokes suggest the improvisational nature of Indian classical music, where the musician explores the raga within its framework but with personal expression. The overlapping and intertwining forms may represent the various melodic movements within the raga Des, known for its grace and fluidity. The circular form, possibly representing the sun or another central motif, might symbolize the cyclic nature of time and rhythm in Indian classical music. In the context of raga Des, this could allude to the cyclical patterns of the taal (rhythmic cycle) and the interplay between the melody and rhythm.

2. Raag Anil Madhyam (PanditSanjoyBandopadhyay- Sitar)^{vi}

Anil Madhyam is a new Raga, and according to the creator Pt. Sanjoy Bandopadhyay, the mood of this raga is serene [shanta] and pathos [karuna], somewhat mystical. It is Shadav raga (having six notes) with highly prominent tivra madhyam. The application of colours in many layers demonstrates the profound emotion. These layers create complexity and richness to the splendid emotional aura of the raga. Highlighted combination of vermilion effectively enhances the prominence of Tivra madhyam, the keynote of the raga. The effect of Komal Gandhara gives Anil Madhyam a very soft and tender feeling and is depicted with cobalt blue, which gives a soft feel as compared to the other colours used in the painting. The bold use of colours emphasize the magnificent character of the raga. The delicate brushstrokes and subtle variations in Colour within each layer create a sense of movement and dynamism, reflecting the raga's flowing melodies and rhythmic patterns.

Overall, it can be deemed that Mishra has been extremely expressive and revolutionary in their approach while painting this raga.

3. Raag Puriya Dhanashree : (Dr.HimanshuVishwaroop - Violin)^{vii}

This painting is a beautiful and evocative representation of Raag Puriya Dhanashree. It captures the various facets of the raga's emotional character through Colour, form, and technique. The smooth transitions between colours and the absence of harsh lines lead to the softness of Dhavai and Rishabh. Blended watercolours convey the softness and subtlety of the Komal Rishabh and Dhavai notes. The prominent use of vermilion and black adds a sense of intensity and power to the painting, reflecting the

"wrathful and fearsome" aspects of the raga. These bold colours create a striking contrast and draw the viewer's attention to certain areas of the composition. The overall sobriety of the scale and the delicate blending of colours contribute to the emotional depth of the painting. This suggests a sense of introspection and contemplation, which aligns with the emotional character of Raag Puriya Dhanashree. The highlighted shades of yellow and the delicate blending of colours could represent the emotional shifts as the raga moves from one note to another. This adds a dynamic element to the painting and invites the viewer to consider the raga's journey.

4. Raga Gurjari Todi : (Dr.HimanshuVishwaroop - Violin)^{viii}

Mishra exhibited a remarkable balance between tenderness and intensity, illustrating the complex expressions and emotional transitions of Gurjari todi. Watercolours blended carefully with gentle washes convey the "pathetic delight" aspect of Gurjari todi. These gentle washes create a sensitive and fragile impact, hinting at the underlying sorrow beneath the surface. The dominant use of yellow and gold tones symbolises the dawn or early morning when raga Gurjari Todi is traditionally performed. The raga has a tranquil and devotional character. Red and orange hues represent the intensity and depth of emotion within the raga's melodic expression. The dark tones throughout the painting add a sense of gravity and depth as per the raga's emotional tone.

The free-flowing forms overlap, suggesting continuity and fluidity in the raga's melodic movement. The raga is known for its elongated, meandering phrases, and this is visually echoed in the brushstrokes that intertwine and merge seamlessly. The central form, which appears to have a halo or arch-like shape, could symbolise divinity or spiritual ascension. This might represent the raga's connection to spiritual themes and its ability to elevate the listener to a higher state of consciousness.

The contrast between the bright and dark areas of the painting represents the balance between the lighter, more delicate aspects of Gurjari Todi and its deeper, more profound emotions. The artist seems to capture how the raga transitions from sorrow to delight, much like the blend of light and darkness at dusk.

The use of negative space, particularly the large area of white in the upper portion of the painting, adds to the sense of longing and vulnerability. It creates a sense of emptiness that echoes the melancholic undercurrent of the raga. The small, scattered dots of vermilion throughout the painting could be interpreted as sparks of anger or passion, punctuating the overall softness of the composition

Findings and Conclusion

Table 1: Comparative analysis of the two Artists based on six basic elements and principles

	Balance	Rhythm	Movement	Contrast	Harmony	Variety
Wassily Kandinsky	Diagonal lines and interlocking forms, vibrant hues and sharp black lines helps to balance the composition	Bold contrast & dynamic shapes evoke the rhythm	Using colours and forms to create a sense of movement & energy	Interplay of warm & cool colours create contrast	Interplay of positive & negative space creates harmony	The varying thickness & texture of strokes add rhythmic variation
Sushil Mishra	Contrast between the bright and dark areas represent the balance	Vibrant colours and dynamic brush strokes suggests rhythm	Overlapping & intertwining forms represent various melodic movements	Bold colours create a striking contrast	Delicate blending of colours with interplay of light & dark creates harmony	Use of delicate brush stroke and subtle variation in colour

Table 1 showcases the comparative analysis done for both artists. They are supporters of abstract expressionism, and their combined heritage is immense. Although they came to life in different cultural spaces, they lived and created in predominantly different environments, and each shared a passion for the unity of arts, so inner expression was more critical for both of them. Trying to break from the traditional figurative painting style, they strained to evoke music's rhythms, structures, and tones in their work—in short, to transform one art form into another.

An important observation regarding all the works studied in this paper is the change in the styles and approaches with the change in the musical experience. Kandinsky painted after attending the concerts and expressed his musical experiences later, while Mishra's paintings are the spontaneous and immediate repercussions of the musical happenings.

In conclusion, this study discovered the differences in emotional responses and interpretation of the musical perception of the two artists, highlighting the uniqueness of their artworks in terms of application of colour, technique and forms. Synesthetic interpretations of both artists, showcasing the multifaceted relationship between music and painting, have been the focal point of this research. Through the comparative analysis of Wassily Kandinsky's abstract paintings and Sushil Mishra's portrayal of Indian Raga music in art, this study has provided a deeper understanding of how different artists approach the depiction of music in their work.

The implications of this study extend beyond the exploration of emotional responses to music and painting. Through the comparative analysis of Kandinsky and Mishra's approaches to depicting music in their art, it becomes evident that artists express unique and individual synaesthetic experiences.

Hence, the analysis suggests that the intersection between music and painting can lead to a diverse spectrum of emotional and sensory experiences for both the creators and the audience. Furthermore, the findings of this study highlight the subjective nature of synesthetic responses and emotional experiences elicited by music and painting.

References

Cytowic RE (2018). *Synesthesia*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press. ISBN 978-0-262-53509-0.

Calkins, M. W. (1893). A statistical study of pseudo-chromesthesia and of mental forms. *The American Journal of Psychology*, 5(4), 439-464.

Critchley, E. M. R. (1994). *Synaesthesia: The neurological boundaries of reality*. Farrand Press.

Jacobs, L., Karpik, A., Bozian, D., & Gøthgen, S. (1981). Auditory-visual synesthesia sound-induced photisms. *Archives of Neurology*, 38(4), 211-216.

Mishra, S. (2013). *Music, nature, and spirituality in abstract art*. In *New dimensions of Indian music* (pp. 1-15). Kanishka Publications & Distributors.

Pragya, P. & Mishra Sushil (2019). *Aesthetic and literary visualisation of Raga*. In Saam Bharati (Seminar proceedings). Kolkata, India.

Spinato, G. (n.d.). *Art encounters music: Kandinsky and Schoenberg*. Academia.edu. Retrieved September 9, 2024, https://www.academia.edu/3769674/Art_encounters_music_Kandinsky_and_Schoenberg

Simner, J. (2012). Title of the article. *British Journal of Psychology*, 103(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1348/000712610x528305>

Ward, J., Huckstep, B., & Tsakanikos, E. (2006). Sound-colour synaesthesia: To what extent does it use cross-modal mechanisms common to us all?. *Cortex*, 42(2), 264-280.

Walker, C. (2014). The language of form and color: Traces of swedenborg's doctrine of correspondences in kandinsky's concerning the spiritual in art. *The New Philosophy*, 117(3-4).

Wassily-Kandinsky.org. (n.d.). *Yellow-Red-Blue* (1925). Retrieved September 9, 2024, from <https://www.wassily-kandinsky.org/Yellow-Red-Blue.jsp>

Jane Trotter (2021, November 15). In harmony: Wassily Kandinsky. *Abstracted Reality*. <https://abstractedreality.com/in-harmony-wassily-kandinsky/>

ⁱ ***Impressions III (Concert)*** was painted by Kandinsky soon after he had attended a concert by Arnold Schonberg in Munich in 1911. <https://mydailyartdisplay.uk/2012/08/04/compositions-impressions-and-improvisations-by-kandinsky/>

ⁱⁱ ***Improvisation 19*** was also completed by Kandinsky in 1911.

<https://mydailyartdisplay.uk/2012/08/04/compositions-impressions-and-improvisations-by-kandinsky/>

ⁱⁱⁱ <https://www.canvasprintsaustralia.net.au/the-role-of-music-in-wassily-kandinskys-abstract-creations/>

^{iv} <https://abstractedreality.com/in-harmony-wassily-kandinsky/>

^v This painting was done in 2011 while listening to Pt. Nikhil Banerjee's recording of raga Des.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yW66Q1bvtc8>

^{vi} This painting was done in 2012 while listening to the newly created raga Anil madhyam by Pt. Sanjoy Bandopadhyay on youtube. <https://youtu.be/t8o3gi5Zg2k?si=iukIWUr-dZLidftF>

^{vii} This was painted in 2016 during a live session of Dr. Himanshu Vishwaroop's performance in Khairagarh.

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